

DOI:

American Animated Father: How Bad Is He?

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Family-based American animated series transmit typical gender stereotypes through the interaction of family members within a fictional family. They provide important insights into how men are portrayed in the mass media and reveal certain beliefs and stereotypes about gender roles in a family. Fathers in family-based animated sitcoms engage in a variety of actions, namely interaction with their children and wives.

Over the past three decades, hearing grownup jokes in kiddie cartoon form has become much less of a novelty. The result is an abundance of adult animation that can feel overwhelming. To stand out in such a packed field, creators are taking big swings and using the familiarity and flexibility of animation to tackle previously taboo subjects (Virtue 2021).

Stan Smith, the protagonist of the animated sitcom *American Dad!*, is depicted as an exaggeratedly masculine husband and father. As the family's breadwinner, he works for the Central Intelligence Agency and tries to apply the same drastic measures and strict rules at work and home.

In the episode *Bully for Steve* (season 6, episode 16) Stan begins to bully his son Steve attempting to make him tougher. Despite different upbringing methods with his wife Francine, he keeps acting violently towards his own son:

Francine: Stop bullying our son!

Stan: It's for his own good. He needs to learn to stand up for himself.

Francine: He's fine the way he is!

Stan: Look, I'm not going to push him around forever, just until he fights back.

Francine: You're crazy!

Steve Smith is an example of traditional masculinity, but his power and authority are expressed through tough attitude, strength and violence. Like Peter Griffin, the protagonist of *Family Guy*, he is depicted as a quite egoistical man, but Peter is even more indifferent towards interests of his children. When Peter's daughter

Stan Smith

Meg speaks about her intentions in the episode Long John Peter (season 6, episode 12), he does not support her but enforces his own ambitions without taking into account her own ones.

Meg: I wanna be a veterinarian when I grow up!

Peter: Meg, we've been over this. You're going to gain 150lbs., and write Ugly Betty fan-fiction.

Meg: But Daaaaaaaad!

Peter: Meg, that's final.

Peter Griffin

A Netflix animated series F is for Family, that is set during the 1970s and features the Murphy family, illustrates a physically and emotionally abusive father Frank as well. In the episode The Bleedin' in Sweden (season 1, episode 1) he purchases a brand new color television to watch a boxing match with his neighbours and says to his children:

Frank: You are not to touch this unless I say so, and I am never gonna say so. Is that understood?

The father of the Murphy family is abusive in the way he treats his children as he does not care about the fact that they also want to watch TV. Moreover, when his son Kevin says he wants to sleep, he shouts at him using obscene language:

Kevin: Guys, I'm trying to sleep!

Frank (shouts): Then close your eyes and shut the f**k up!

Frank Murphy

As has been noted, fictional fathers in American animated series represent stereotypical masculinity in a rather insulting way, neglecting and offending their offspring. In the animated discourse, they are undermined to such an extent that they are regarded as abusers to the family.